

**MOBILE APPLICATION AS A TOOL FOR INTEGRATION AND SERVICE
PROMOTION IN THE SECTORAL LIBRARY OF THE MULTICAMPUS
SCHOOL OF MEDICAL SCIENCES OF RN**

APLICACIÓN MÓVIL COMO HERRAMIENTA DE INTEGRACIÓN Y PROMOCIÓN DE
SERVICIOS EN LA BIBLIOTECA SECTORIAL DE LA ESCUELA MULTICAMPI DE
CIENCIAS MÉDICAS DE RN

APLICATIVO MÓVEL COMO FERRAMENTA DE INTEGRAÇÃO E PROMOÇÃO DE
SERVIÇOS NA BIBLIOTECA SETORIAL DA ESCOLA MULTICAMPI DE CIÊNCIAS
MÉDICAS DO RN

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Abstract

Academic libraries have increasingly adopted digital and electronic formats to meet the growing demands of a technological society. The Dr. Paulo Bezerra Sectoral Library of the Multicampus School of Medical Sciences of Rio Grande do Norte provides a wide range of products and services to both academic and external communities. However, it faces challenges in promoting and enhancing the visibility of these resources. This study aimed to develop a mobile application to improve access to and visibility of the library's products and services, fostering more effective user engagement. The research was exploratory, applied, and qualitative, conducted as a case study. The application was created using Glide Apps and incorporates features such as information retrieval tools and direct communication channels. The evaluation, conducted with 52 participants, emphasized the app's practicality, intuitiveness, and relevance as a tool for academic integration. It is concluded that the application successfully addresses the community's informational needs, enhancing the visibility and accessibility of the library's services.

Palavras-chave na segunda língua: Libraries Digital; Libraries Medical; Mobile Applications.

Resumen

Las bibliotecas académicas han adoptado cada vez más formatos digitales y electrónicos para responder a las crecientes demandas de una sociedad tecnológica. La Biblioteca Sectorial Dr. Paulo Bezerra de la Escuela Multicampi de Ciencias Médicas de Rio Grande do Norte ofrece una amplia gama de productos y servicios a las comunidades académica y externa. Sin embargo, enfrenta desafíos para promover y aumentar la visibilidad de estos recursos. Este estudio tuvo como objetivo desarrollar una aplicación móvil para mejorar el acceso y la visibilidad de los productos y servicios de la biblioteca, fomentando una interacción más efectiva con los usuarios. La investigación fue de carácter exploratorio, aplicada y cualitativa, llevada a cabo como un estudio de caso. La aplicación fue desarrollada utilizando Glide Apps, e incluye funcionalidades como herramientas de búsqueda de información y canales de comunicación directa. La evaluación, realizada con 52 participantes, destacó la practicidad, la intuición y la relevancia de la aplicación como herramienta de integración académica. Se concluye que la aplicación satisface las necesidades informativas de la comunidad, mejorando la visibilidad y el acceso a los servicios de la biblioteca.

Palabras clave: Bibliotecas Digitales; Bibliotecas Médicas; Aplicaciones Móviles.

Resumo

As bibliotecas acadêmicas têm adotado o formato digital/eletrônico em resposta às demandas crescentes da sociedade tecnológica. A Biblioteca Setorial Dr. Paulo Bezerra da Escola Multicampi de Ciências Médicas do Rio Grande do Norte oferece uma variedade de produtos e serviços à comunidade acadêmica e externa. No entanto, enfrenta desafios em promover e dar visibilidade a esses recursos. Este estudo teve como objetivo desenvolver um aplicativo móvel para facilitar o acesso e ampliar a visibilidade dos produtos e serviços da biblioteca, promovendo uma interação mais eficiente com os usuários. A pesquisa teve caráter exploratório, aplicado e qualitativo, sendo conduzida como um estudo de caso. O aplicativo foi desenvolvido por meio do Glide Apps, incluindo recursos como busca de informações e canais de comunicação direta. A avaliação do aplicativo, realizada com 52 participantes, destacou sua praticidade, intuitividade e relevância como ferramenta de integração acadêmica. Conclui-se que o aplicativo atende às necessidades informacionais da comunidade, potencializando a visibilidade e a utilização dos serviços da biblioteca.

Palavras-chave: Bibliotecas Digitais; Bibliotecas Médicas; Aplicativos Móveis.

Introduction

University libraries (UL) have their roots in religious institutions and expanded from the 12th century onwards, coinciding with the emergence of the first European universities. Thus, information, previously stored in places with restricted access, could be viewed and disseminated more widely, to democratize knowledge in support of teaching and scientific research (Vianna, 2013; Silveira, 2014). At the time, teachers were allowed to use a single copy of the collection to read aloud to their students (Carvalho, 2004).

Driven by technological advances and social changes, libraries have transformed over time, playing a fundamental role in the global academic scene. In the 17th century, scientific journals appeared, and after the French Revolution (1789), a movement began to diversify scientific communication, which facilitated the emergence of specialized libraries, expanding their role from mere repositories of information to active agents in the dissemination of knowledge. At the beginning of the 20th century, libraries became accessible to the public, making their collections available on shelves for common use by society (Ferreira, 2021).

In Brazil, the creation of libraries dates to the colonial period, with the arrival of religious orders in the Jesuits, Franciscans, Carmelites and Benedictines, when what can be called the process of instruction began. The growing demand for books to instruct children, but also teachers, led to the emergence of libraries in various provinces such as Salvador and Espírito Santo, followed in the 17th century by the colleges of Rio de Janeiro, São Paulo, Olinda, Recife, Maranhão and Pará (Nunes; Carvalho, 2016).

Moving into the contemporary context, Paulo Freire has had a significant influence on Brazilian public universities and the educational system. The "Pedagogy of the Oppressed" was a milestone in teaching and research practices in institutions for the discussion about the inclusion of students, valuing the individual life experiences of each one to create more accessible environments (Freire, 2005). For the author, reading is to seek to create an understanding of what has been read and to teach reading is to engage in creative experience around understanding.

In the context of understanding and disseminating knowledge, university libraries occupy a prominent place today, playing a fundamental role in scientific, technological, cultural and social development. They act as catalysts and disseminators of knowledge,

bringing together and providing resources for researchers, teachers and students. As knowledge centers par excellence, university libraries, like all other information units, have evolved. They have come to meet not only the information needs of the public but have also kept pace with changes in the field of information and communication technologies, as well as changes in user behavior levels, which are increasingly connected to the digital world (Silveira, 2014).

In this context, understanding the evolution of these institutions helps to deepen discussions about the role of libraries as community spaces dedicated to access to knowledge. In this sense, libraries play a crucial role in this process, providing favorable environments to promote this understanding through interaction with various materials and resources (Rosa, 2021).

With the advent of the Internet, a significant advance in technological evolution that influences social behavior, a new perspective has emerged on university library patrons. Previously considered specialized, they are now seen as interdisciplinary. This transition not only affects users, but also the entire technical team, which must adjust to new technological challenges to meet the information needs of an increasingly connected community (Carvalho, 2004; Cunha, 2008).

Currently, university libraries operate in multiple formats, combining physical and digital resources to meet the diverse demands of users. According to Oliveira (2007), the pioneering use of computers connected to the Internet has improved the effectiveness of the services offered by libraries. Consequently, users are making greater use of resources such as electronic journals, digital libraries, electronic archives and repositories, which requires constant updating on the part of the professional and information systems involved.

As a result, university libraries are increasingly adapting to the digital environment, offering a wide variety of resources and services to meet the demands of contemporary users. However, this transition to the digital environment requires a continuous effort to update and adapt to the part of both professionals and information systems.

The Internet emerged during the 20th century, bringing with it Automated Libraries that use computers for their operation. At that time, the computerization process was mainly focused on training professional staff to digitize the collection (Cunha, 2008). In the 21st

century, society is immersed in the so-called 4th Industrial Revolution – the Age of the Autonomous Library, *U-Library* or *Mobile Library*. Consequently, university libraries are no longer restricted by physical barriers, information is now accessed through a variety of technological devices, such as laptops, smartphones, tablets and on social media platforms, where users are connected to the network, whether *online* or *offline* (Silveira, 2014). This era brings with it new paradigms and habits of research and information consumption in the academic community within the university environment (Pieranti; Domingues, 2022).

However, despite the progress, the pace and scope of technological modernisation in Brazil is not uniform. As Marcondes, Mendonça and Carvalho (2006) observed after analysing the websites of 209 (two hundred and nine) university libraries across the country, most of these libraries only have an online catalogue, highlighting the need to incorporate more links to access information. Initiatives of this nature are essential to ensure that access to high-quality scientific communication is equitably available to all users.

In this scenario, creating robust web pages can entail significant costs (Marcondes; Mendonça; Carvalho, 2006). For this reason, investing in the development of mobile applications may prove to be a viable alternative. In Brazil, 200 (two hundred) apps developed by federal educational institutions were identified, duly registered with the National Institute of Intellectual Property (INPI) and the *Google Play Store*, 21% of which were designed by federal universities located in the Northeast region (Dantas; Galhardo; Diniz, 2023).

Mobile devices are praised for their portability, ease of use and connectivity, accompanying users everywhere. They facilitate instant communication and interaction at any time and place, allowing users to access information and communicate without the limitations of space and time (Rodrigues; Foresti; Viera, 2021). These distinctive characteristics of mobile users and mobile devices underline the importance of adapting library services to meet the needs and expectations of this increasingly connected and technologically immersed public.

Jesus and Cunha (2019) talk about the need to invest in technological innovation as it is essential for libraries to keep up with the demands and expectations of users, who are increasingly connected and familiar with advanced technologies. This investment can involve

the development of mobile applications, digital platforms, integrated management systems, process automation, among other solutions that make library services more efficient, accessible and attractive to the academic community.

The research also showed that the main purpose of these applications is to meet the needs of academic administration and management. Therefore, despite the flexibility of the applications, their use is still restricted and little explored for other opportunities to integrate services and products, such as those offered by academic libraries. These applications are already available at the University of São Paulo (USP), with various functionalities, and at the State University of Rio Grande do Norte (UERN).

At UFRN, the Zila Mamede central library has an app - app.bczm.ufrn.br, which has two icons directed to the Integrated System for the Management of Academic Activities (SIGAA), a platform that centralizes academic and administrative services - "UFRN Libraries" and to institutional repositories. Despite this, the Dr. Paulo Bezerra Sector Library (BS-EMCM), which is in the Multicampi School of Medical Sciences of Rio Grande do Norte, belonging to the Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte in Caicó (RN), does not have the facilities of a mobile library, which combines the information services offered to users with the use of mobile devices (DM) (Vassilakaki, 2014). Mobile libraries offer services such as ebooks, an online catalog, communication via text messages (SMS or apps), the use of QR codes (*Quick Response*), among other options (Hassan *et al.*, 2015; Liu; Briggs, 2015).

The Dr. Paulo Bezerra Sectorial Library (BS-EMCM) covers an area of 208.68 m² and is fully air-conditioned, offering both physical and digital collections. The books are catalogued and organized on double-sided steel shelves, occupying an area of 100.30 m², and are borrowed through the UFRN library system. The digital collection is available in the SIGAA public catalog (Library Module), accessible through the "UFRN Libraries" application. In the virtual collection, users, both students and teachers, can access the "My Library" platform; ABNT collections via the *proxy server*; digital books published by the UFRN University Press (EDUFRN) and the Distance Education Department (SEDIS); CAPES Periodicals Portal; UFRN Electronic Periodicals Portal; Institutional Repository (IR); Accessible Information Repository (RIA) and the *UpToDate* platform (EMCM, 2023).

There is therefore a significant opportunity for university libraries to explore and extend their services through mobile applications, taking advantage of the ubiquity of mobile devices and the needs of the contemporary mobile user. This approach can offer a more convenient, personalized and efficient experience for users, while expanding the reach and impact of university libraries on the academic community.

The main objective of this study was to develop a mobile application for the Dr. Paulo Bezerra Sector Library, with the aim of increasing the visibility of its products and services, facilitating access to information and promoting more efficient interaction with its users. In addition, the study documented the process of designing and developing the application, offering insights for future similar initiatives.

Methodology

This research is of an applied, objective nature, aimed at solving specific problems. It has an exploratory nature, which means exploring and understanding the subject in question more broadly and deeply. It also adopts a qualitative approach, recognizing the inseparable link between the objective world and subjectivity, which cannot be translated into quantitative numbers alone (Gil, 2007).

The technical procedures of this research, according to (Gil, 2007), is a case study, a research technique that thoroughly investigates a single instance, such as a person, group, organization or situation, to obtain a deeper and more comprehensive understanding of the object of study, identifying its unique characteristics, peculiarities and possible causal relationships. This approach has significant potential for both theoretical and practical advances in various areas of research, as pointed out by Gerring (2019).

Information was collected in two main stages: qualitative and quantitative.

Qualitative information was obtained through meetings with library staff, semi-structured interviews and direct observations of the sectors. These procedures made it possible to map users' needs and identify the priority functionalities for the

application. The qualitative data was analyzed based on thematic categorization, according to the methodology proposed by Bardin (2011), looking for patterns and trends that would guide the application's development stages.

The app was evaluated using a public opinion poll using the Mentimeter® tool, which generates word clouds. Fifty-two users took part, including teachers, students and administrative staff. These participants were asked to express their perception of the app by providing words or phrases that summarise their experience.

In addition, the results were analyzed based on the theoretical framework of system usability and user satisfaction (Nielsen, 1993; ISO 9241-11, 2021). The answers obtained were grouped into thematic categories for a critical analysis of the main impressions, facilitating the identification of improvements and adjustments needed to the application.

Participants linked to the academic community of the RN Multicampi School of Medical Sciences, with access to the application's functionalities, were included. There were no specific exclusions, apart from technical limitations such as the unavailability of compatible devices. The survey was carried out remotely, with digital access to the app and the collection of opinions via an online platform, ensuring practicality and accessibility.

In accordance with CNS Resolution 510/2016, the research was classified as public opinion, with no possibility of identifying the participants, as the data was collected anonymously and voluntarily. Therefore, the requirement to submit to the CEP/Conep System, according to Article 2, XIV of the aforementioned Resolution, did not apply.

- Building the app

The design and development phases of the application were defined and coordinated in collaboration with the staff of the EMCM/RN sector library. The app was designed and developed in four phases, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Stages of the survey and development of the mobile application for the Dr. Paulo Bezerra Sector Library

Source: Own elaboration.

STEP 1 – Survey of Library Sectors

For this phase, meetings were scheduled with library staff, as well as technical visits to specific departments (Reception; Collection; Materials loan; Individual study rooms; Group study rooms; Technical processing and conservation area; Librarians' room), technical staff (librarians, technicians and trainees), services (Exhibitions) and products (Online platforms). The meetings made it possible to discuss goals and expectations, while the visits provided direct observations and interviews with the technical team. These activities were crucial to identifying the needs of each department and guiding the development of the application according to the expectations of the library staff and end users.

STEP 2 – Developing the application interface

The interface was designed on the *Glide App* website (<http://www.glideapps.com>), as suggested by Rahmawati *et al.* (2021). This decision was made to implement an effective and easily accessible solution for users. The design includes the library's logo and graphic typography (fonts and colors) that facilitate access to information. The layout of the information has been made clear and accessible to users, with access buttons for specific categories. This allows for simplified navigation and makes it easier to locate the desired information. In addition, direct links have been included to access the products available, such as virtual platforms, information resources and services offered by the library.

STEP 3 – Preparation of multimedia material

Photographic records of the library's different sectors were taken to allow visual identification and better familiarization of users with the library's *layout* via the app. The idea behind this is to contribute to a more intuitive and efficient user experience, especially for those who don't frequently use the library's physical space.

STEP 4 – Evaluating the application

The app was evaluated quantitatively using the word cloud feature of the Mentimeter tool. This method offers the advantage of collecting data anonymously, guaranteeing user privacy as it does not identify users individually. As a result, there is no need to obtain approval from the Research Ethics Committee.

Using the word cloud in the Mentimeter tool allows users to express their opinions, perceptions and *feedback* on the app freely and spontaneously. Through this tool, they can enter words or phrases that describe their experiences, impressions and suggestions regarding the app. This process provides a comprehensive overview of users' main impressions, identifying areas that may require improvement.

In this way, the quantitative approach enables an objective and measurable analysis of the data obtained through the word cloud. The most frequent or highlighted words in the word cloud can provide trends, areas of focus or concerns shared by users.

Results

To build the application, a survey was carried out, written in script format to make it easier to configure when building the platform.

Figure 2 - Application login screen: access to functionalities via institutional e-mail

Source: Own elaboration.

Figure 2-A shows the *login* interface of the Dr. Paulo Bezerra Sectorial Library application, where users can access various functions using their institutional e-mail address. The application was designed to facilitate access to the products and services of the Dr. Paulo Bezerra Sector Library. The home page presents general information about the library, such as its address, opening hours and recent updates. It offers navigation buttons that take users directly to specific services, such as loans, reserving materials and guidance on using digital platforms.

The "Technical Team" tab shows images and descriptions of the library's team members, including their names, roles, institutional contacts and areas of expertise. This feature aims to promote greater interaction between users and the professionals responsible, allowing for personalized and efficient support. In the "Talk to the Library" tab, users have access to a digital form for sending questions, suggestions and requests to reserve spaces or exhibitions. This channel is integrated with the library's systems, guaranteeing quick responses and agile service.

The application also integrates direct links to essential virtual platforms, such as the SIGAA online catalog, "My Library" and the CAPES Periodicals Portal. Each link is accompanied by a brief description of its functionality, guiding users who may not be familiar with these tools. To facilitate navigation in the library's physical space, images of the different sectors are associated with interactive icons. By clicking on an icon, the user can access detailed information about the corresponding sector, including physical collection, study rooms and technical services.

The structure of the application has been designed so that products and services can be accessed with a maximum of two clicks, prioritizing efficiency and simplicity. This organization reflects the commitment to offering intuitive and practical user experience, in line with the needs of the academic community.

The services offered by the Sector Library are varied and range from registration for personalized alert services and new acquisitions to support for using the resources offered, including bibliographic commutation, home loans, interlibrary loans, special loans, guidance on standardization, research, ISSN and ISBN requests and copyright. Catalographic records are also requested, the importance of which is related to academic productions, being an essential stage in the procedures following the defence of a dissertation, for example. These services are intrinsically linked to the promotion, dissemination and effective use of information, and are specifically aimed at meeting the needs of UFRN's academic community.

To evaluate this collaborative process, a word cloud made up of 156 terms was generated, as shown in Figure 3, which represents users' impressions and feedback. Through the analysis of this word cloud, the application was described as "intuitive", "practical" and "necessary" by users.

smartphones are identified as emblems of a "digital way of life" and are widespread in contemporary society (Rodrigues; Foresti; Viera, 2021). To meet this demand, libraries need to adopt innovative approaches and develop digital media and platforms with easy access and resources available with good interactivity.

Mobile users play a fundamental role in the process of developing an app, and it is essential that they participate actively from its conception to its realization (Paterson; Low, 2011). For this reason, the development of this app was carried out in collaboration with the entire university community and its effectiveness was evaluated by them.

As a result of this collaborative process, a word cloud was generated consisting of 156 terms that reflect the impressions and opinions of the research participants. These words reflect the users' positive perception of the application's usability and usefulness. By describing it as "intuitive", users suggest that its interface is easy to understand and use, providing a fluid and uncomplicated browsing experience. This feature is crucial to ensure that users can access library resources quickly and efficiently, without the need for additional guidance.

Similarly, by describing the app as "practical", users highlight its ability to meet needs in a pragmatic and effective way. The app offers information that makes it easier to find out about library-related services, such as renewing loans and accessing online resources. This practicality is key to ensuring that users can find out about the services offered by the library, even when they are on the move or away from campus.

Finally, by describing the application as "necessary", users emphasize its importance and relevance to their academic and research activities. This suggests that the app has become an essential tool for users in their daily lives, providing quick and practical access to information and resources that are fundamental to their information needs. Although the app does not allow activities and research to be carried out directly on it, its ability to provide up-to-date information and facilitate access to library services contributes significantly to the efficiency and effectiveness of users' activities.

In this way, constantly updating, using and evaluating the application can guarantee its effectiveness in integrating and expanding the services and information made available by the library. This continuous *feedback* cycle is necessary to ensure the improvement of this media, the expansion of the services offered and greater interactivity with the EMCM/RN sector library team.

According to Barroca-Filho and Aquino (2013), information systems are evolving to adapt to user mobility. However, some obstacles, such as compatibility problems between browsers and mobile devices, support and costs, can make it difficult for institutions to adopt these media. For this reason, in this research, we opted for the *glide apps* tool, which is free, requires no prior knowledge of programming and offers free facilities for managing data and carrying out updates via a database spreadsheet (rows and columns format).

Through *Glide Apps*, other areas of research have already made use of it, successfully used as in nutrition (Miranti *et al.*, 2021), which highlights its effectiveness and versatility in different contexts. This approach provides a viable solution for the creation and implementation of mobile applications, allowing institutions to offer services and information in a more accessible and effective way for users, while overcoming traditional challenges related to mobility and compatibility of information systems.

Ensuring the effective integration of conventional library services with other relevant services and databases is an essential measure to promote a more dynamic and meaningful interaction between users and the institution. By establishing institutional two-way connections, you significantly extend the reach of your collection and services. This allows users to access a diversity of materials and information sources, enriching their research and learning experience. Integration with these external resources facilitates the discovery of relevant content, providing users with a more efficient way of finding information pertinent to their interests and needs. This represents a contemporary way of promoting user interaction with libraries (Laudano *et al.*, 2016).

On the other hand, by allowing other services and databases to access the library's resources, the institution promotes wider collaboration and the exchange of knowledge. This can result in strategic partnerships that benefit both the library and

other organizations or research institutions. The effective integration of library services with other online resources also reflects a proactive approach to keeping up with technological trends and changing user needs. In an increasingly digitized and interconnected world, offering transparent and fluid access to a variety of information sources is key to maintaining the relevance and usefulness of the library as a center of knowledge and learning (Laudano *et al.*, 2016).

Libraries in Brazil are constantly looking for ways to improve the accessibility and convenience of their services, especially in the growing context of mobile device use. This effort to adapt to users' needs reflects libraries' commitment to providing efficient and agile access to information in an increasingly digitized world (Viera; Varvakis; Foresti, 2018).

Examples of successful experiences can be seen in initiatives such as that of the Central Library of the University of São Paulo (USP), which has developed an app to integrate loan services, reservations and consultation of digital materials in a single environment (Jesu; Cunha, 2019). Another important reference is the use of QR codes by the University of Hong Kong, which facilitates quick access to specific library resources (Li, 2013).

The implementation of QR codes or NFC (*Near Field Communication*) simplifies access to library services and serves as a link between the physical and digital worlds (Hoy, 2013). For the EMCM/UFRN sector library, the QR code was used to make it easier for users to download the application. By adopting the use of QR codes, the sector library directs access to the application, eliminating obstacles and encouraging greater participation by teachers, technicians and students. These cases show how adopting technology can not only extend the reach of services but also create more efficient communication with users.

The results of this research corroborate the idea that the adoption of mobile technologies in libraries should be seen as an ongoing process that requires constant monitoring and a permanent dialog with users. The experience with the development and evaluation of this app highlights the importance of aligning technological innovation with the practical needs of users, ensuring that the library remains a relevant and dynamic space in the academic ecosystem.

Final considerations

The creation of this application represents an innovative working tool, free of charge, for all those involved in the teaching-learning process at EMCM/UFRN. It was not expensive for the public education system and did not require any prior knowledge of programming languages. All that was needed was mastery of spreadsheets and interaction with the *glide apps web* tool.

With the implementation of the app, users will have simplified access to resources such as loans, catalogue queries, information on digital platforms and direct communication channels with the technical team. These advances not only facilitate access to information but also create a more interactive and dynamic environment for the academic community, strengthening the library's role as a support center for research, teaching and extension.

The results showed that the application is considered intuitive, practical and necessary by the participants, indicating that it meets the expectations of users who are connected and aligned with today's technological demands. More than a support tool, the app is positioned as an essential facilitator for the effective use of library services, helping to strengthen communication between the library and its audiences.

However, it must be recognized that the continuity of this initiative depends on regular updates, collecting feedback from users and integration with other institutional platforms. Publicity campaigns and training can maximize the adoption and impact of the app on the academic routine. Future research could explore the incorporation of new functionalities, such as personalized services based on artificial intelligence, and evaluate the long-term impacts of using the app on the user experience.

Awareness and promotion campaigns can be carried out to increase user adoption and engagement with the app, using marketing materials and demonstration events to highlight its benefits. Monitoring and data analysis can be implemented to track the use and performance of the app over time, providing *insights* into usage patterns and areas of interest to users.

In short, the application developed reinforces the transformative role of university libraries in the digital age, offering practical solutions that respond directly to the needs of their users and promote greater reach and effectiveness of library services. With this, the Dr. Paulo Bezerra Sector Library reaffirms its commitment to innovation and excellence in supporting the academic community.

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